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Human capital in today's world

In today's fast and furious world, there is a race for virtually everything and found in all walks of life. Among others, this has led to rapid changes within the corporate world as a result of which phenomenal changes have been witnessed. There is also the factor of freedom of choice and how judiciously space is given to an individual to partake of it.

But the crucial factor, perhaps more crucial than anything else is that of human capital and questions such as whether it is motivated or not and whether it is being channeled into where it is needed.

Pakistan is one of those countries where a great chunk of population happens to be young and is bustling with energy. How well the youth are trained and how well their talent and skills are put to use for the betterment of the country matters a lot. The country needs to tap into this chunk and not only that but get the best out of it. Sadly today, the aspect of motivation is missing; the youth are disoriented and are at a loss to figure out what is it and in what direction they should be treading. The coming age is of software and technology. We need to ask ourselves do we have the kind of work force ready to fulfill the country's needs towards that end. Those who are qualified and really talented move away for greener pastures largely in the Middle Eastern countries. This is continuing to cause a severe shortage of able and skilled human capital and sadly every time there is a need for either technical experts, say for instance mining the Thar coal reserves, we have to look to foreign countries.

Pakistan needs to educate and empower its youth with special emphasis on science and IT studies. The youth needs to be assured that their country is there to help them.

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